

Knowledge, Complexity, and Cognitive Processes: Some Reflections on Natural and Artificial Intelligence

Giovanni Maria Guazzo
Hull Institute, Salerno, Italy

Article History:

Received: 29.07.2025 Revised: 13.08.2025 Accepted: 14.08.2025 Published: 16.08.2025

Abstract

Knowledge involves selecting information from the outside world and orienting one's behaviour based on both past experiences and new situations, creating the conditions for studying complex adaptive systems and the emerging phenomena associated with them. The complexity of a system, therefore, is a property of the currently available scientific representation of the system model, consisting of the observer who constructs the model and the model itself. However, complexity does not only include the quantity of units and interactions, but also uncertainties, indeterminacies, and random phenomena.

These considerations should put an end to the endless pseudo-philosophical discussions on the relationship between mind and computer, sparked by developments in “Artificial Intelligence”. The fundamental goals of research in the field of Artificial Intelligence are not so much to build systems that ‘imitate’ humans exactly, but rather to build systems that are “better” than current computers. In other words, what matters most is to have artificial systems that are “useful” to us, with which we can interact “naturally”, enabling computers to simulate complex “reasoning” and other cognitive activities that have until now been exclusive to natural intelligence.

Keywords: *Knowledge, Complexity, Cognitive Processes, Natural Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence.*

Suggested citation: Guazzo, G.M. (2025). Knowledge, Complexity, and Cognitive Processes: Some Reflections on Natural and Artificial Intelligence. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(5), 8-14. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(5\).02](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(5).02)

Introduction

Knowing means selecting information from the outside world and orienting one's behaviour according to both past experiences and new situations. Therefore, hypothesizing the construction of a psychologically correct model, theory, and practice can mean satisfying the need for contemporary scientific knowledge and overcoming dichotomies (symbolic paradigm and sub symbolic paradigm, declarative representation and procedural representation, digital code and analog code), which are so often abused in psychology, in favour of an integration of different points of view that takes into

account the advantages offered by each. This is based on the phenomenological conviction that attention must always be paid to all the “problems at stake,” even when they are extraordinarily complex or contrary to expectations (Morin, 2007).

The concept of ‘complexity’ is playing a critical role in science, highlighting a new alliance between philosophy and science (overcoming the presumed exhaustiveness of their theoretical models and an ‘alliance’ between the perspectives that contribute to the construction of a general discourse on complexity and knowledge), a new way of doing science

(bottom-up, i.e., 'from the bottom up': more in line with the way a system is organized in nature) and a new conception of natural evolution (abandoning the idea that progress governs the history of life) (Prigogine & Stengers, 1984).

It can be defined as the interdisciplinary study of systems composed of a vast number of elements interacting according to defined rules and subject to specific constraints, to understand global behaviours and predict the evolution of emerging phenomena associated with them. The so-called 'complexity of a system' is therefore a property of the currently available scientific representation of the system model, consisting of a) the observer who constructs the model and b) the model itself. Adopting this perspective means abandoning the objectivism of classical science, i.e., viewing the world as a set of manipulable and measurable objects, and taking a relational and dialogical point of view towards being. In short, the complexity of a system refers to the degree of interconnection and interaction between its components, which makes it difficult to predict or understand its overall behaviour based on knowledge of the individual elements. A complex system is characterised by numerous, often non-linear, relationships between its components and the environment, which can lead to emergent behaviours, i.e., behaviours that are not easily deduced from the simple sum of the behaviours characterised by numerous, often non-linear, relationships between its components and the environment, which can lead to emergent behaviours, i.e., behaviours that are not easily deduced from the simple sum of the behaviours of the individual elements.

All complex systems have specific common characteristics: 1) they are made up of several more or less complex components (in general, the more numerous and complex the subsystems that make it up, the more complex the system as a whole), 2) these components interact by passing information to each other, but the information they exchange cannot be too numerous (otherwise the system becomes chaotic) or too few (the system 'crystallizes'), 3) if there is a leading component that alone governs the behavior of the whole, the system is not complex, and 4) the more factors that influence the system's adaptation to the

environment (learning, interaction with the system observer, cooperation, communication, etc.), the more complex the system is.

All human systems are in a state of unstable equilibrium, both with one another and with their environment. Three situations can arise during the evolution of the system: a) the system reaches a point (attractor) from which, despite any external disturbances, it no longer deviates (state of order), b) the system moves irregularly and is always unstable in the space of states (state of chaos) and c) the system converges towards specific points (attractors), but any disturbances can destabilize it (state of "edge of chaos") (Guazzo, 1987, 2003).

The "edge of chaos" is the optimal state of equilibrium that makes self-organisation (spontaneous organisation of the components of the system) possible. When a complex adaptive system self-organises, new and unpredictable phenomena emerge, called "emergent phenomena." A phenomenon is said to be emerging if and only if: a) it is processual, b) it can be described using a language that is qualitatively different from that used to describe the other properties of the system with which it is associated, c) the system model does not predict its behaviour, and d) its existence does not depend on the existence of individual components of the system. Emerging phenomena, such as learning and thinking associated with the central nervous system of human beings, are therefore the same phenomena that make our existence possible and make it what we know it to be (Harth, 1983).

However, complexity encompasses not only quantities of units and interactions, but also uncertainties, indeterminacies, and random phenomena.

The elements that characterise the "universe of complexity" can therefore be recognised starting from the issues of uncertainty and imprecision (Prigogine & Stengers, 1997). With the "discovery" of complexity, the myths of certainty and completeness of knowledge begin to crumble.

From this point of view, the reformulation of knowledge is radical, with the reintroduction of

imprecision into a universe that felt destined for the triumphant and unstoppable conquest of 'truth' and believed that anything that could not be quantified and formalised did not exist.

In this context, what role does Artificial Intelligence (AI) play? Are AI applications opposed to those of Natural Intelligence (NI) or are they isomorphic? Will AI be able to develop its form of "awareness" or "consciousness" in the future? We will try to answer these questions in the following paragraph.

Natural Intelligence and Artificial Intelligence

Many theories on the relationship between cybernetics and cognitive activities have been proposed for many years, but only now are they attracting the attention of experts and the public, who seem to be "rediscovering" their importance. This is mainly due to recent developments in the field of Artificial Intelligence, following rapid advances in technological innovation (the construction of logic chips that process large volumes of data at ever-increasing speeds), which have forcefully raised the issue of computers performing activities typically considered "human". In this sector, there already seems to be growing and uncritical enthusiasm for the possibility of artificial intelligence solving any 'intelligent' problem, which has taken extreme forms, such as those who see machines replacing humans in all activities. To avoid easy enthusiasm or easy disapproval, it is necessary to clarify the limits, meaning, and value of these models and the simulations conducted based on them. Only in this way is it possible to escape the suggestions of the current fashion trend and develop a critical awareness of potential developments in this field (Pessa, 1992).

To this end, it is necessary first to introduce the distinction between a model of a physical or neurophysiological process and a simulation of the same. It is very convenient to schematically represent such a process as characterized by a set A of possible initial events A_1, A_2, A_3, \dots , a set B of possible final events B_1, B_2, B_3, \dots and a set T of transformations T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots each of which causes one or more events in set A to pass to one

or more events in set B. If we imagine each of the three sets, A, B, and T, as having a "structure" deriving from the existence of "internal" relations between the events belonging to A, other 'internal' relations between the events of B and, similarly, for the transformations of T, we can easily introduce the concept of a "(mathematical) model of the process characterized by A, B, T"; more precisely, the model is provided by three sets of abstract mathematical entities, denoted respectively by A', B', T' , such that A' is isomorphic to A, B' is isomorphic to B, and T' is isomorphic to T. In other words, in a model, the sets of mathematical entities that correspond to the initial and final events and the transformations of the real process have the same structure as the sets of real entities that characterise the process in question (Rosen, 1986; Pessa, 1987).

The difference between a model and a simulation of a process stems from the fact that, in the latter, the identity of structure only concerns the initial and final events, but not necessarily the transformations. This means that, while in simulation we attempt to represent the initial and final events in a manner identical to reality, the transformations that connect these events do not, in general, have any relationship with those that occur in the real process (Guazzo, 1987a).

The distinction we have just introduced serves, among other things, to clarify the fact that a computer can 'simulate' human behaviour (using a special program) without being a 'model' of that behaviour; thus, for example, the fact that there are computer programs that assemble puzzle pieces only serves to demonstrate that it is possible to devise algorithms to fit together, based on shape and design, the initial and final positions of small pieces of cardboard to reconstruct the original image, but it says nothing about the processes that take place in a human being (whether child or adult) when assembling a puzzle. These considerations should put an end to the endless pseudo-philosophical discussions on the relationship between mind and computer, sparked by developments in what is unfortunately termed "Artificial Intelligence" (Pessa, 1992).

From what we have said so far, a crucial question now arises: Are theories about the functioning of the nervous system, the brain, or the “mind” models or simulations?

Before answering this question, it is worth describing some fundamental aspects of brain processes, including:

a) *the existence of different levels of analysis and description.* The brain is a highly complex system composed of numerous components that interact at various levels. Some characteristics of its behaviour can be observed at the *macroscopic level*, i.e., at the level of observations that can be made on the scale of everyday life (e.g., the motor acts that allow us to grasp objects or the responses we give to a test); other characteristics can only be observed at the *microscopic level* (e.g., the discharges of individual neurons). However, these levels are not independent but interact with each other in a complex manner: for example, our motor actions and even our thoughts are influenced by individual patterns of neuronal discharge, and our thoughts can affect the biochemical reactions that occur in a complex manner: for example, our motor actions and even our thoughts are influenced by individual patterns of neuronal discharge, and our thoughts can influence the biochemical reactions that occur at the cellular level.

b) *dynamism.* The brain is not a static system, but a constantly evolving entity that changes over time. However, many different processes of change coexist simultaneously, characterised by different rates of change and therefore by various *time scales*. In general, the processes that give rise to profound structural changes (such as the processes of synaptic efficiency modification, which some believe to be at the basis of learning processes) are characterized by very long time scales (hours, days, etc.), while scales of the order of milliseconds or hundredths of a second represent the processes of discharge and therefore of change in electrochemical potential differences.

c) *the absence of a predefined logical architecture.* Although it is possible to identify subsystems in the brain that form a kind of architecture (e.g., the various cortical systems, the thalamus, the hippocampus, and the cerebellum), there is no

similarity between this architecture and that of a digital computer. In the latter, the various connections and modes of operation of the multiple modules are carefully designed. In contrast, in the brain, the connections and roles of individual components are difficult to define, and they vary over time and depending on the tasks performed by the individual. In short, it can be said that the brain is a system that exploits *noise* and *disorder* to function; everything that the brain produces (actions, thoughts, decisions, language, reasoning, etc.) *emerges* from a low-level activity that is devoid of any order and in which the role of individual components (such as neurons) seems almost irrelevant.

The answer to the previous question can therefore be given by referring to the neurophysiological processes which, whatever point of view is adopted, are the physical substrate of all ‘higher’ activities: cognitive, emotional, affective, and so on. Experimental evidence suggests that these processes occur in tissues composed of many elementary units interconnected in a highly complex manner. It can be safely stated, at the current state of scientific development, that while we are now able to develop sufficiently realistic “models” of the behaviour of individual elementary units, considered in isolation, this is not yet possible for the global behaviour of tissues. It follows that the theoretical description of the latter is, for now, only possible through mathematical “simulations” (Auchmuty & Nicolis, 1975).

This allows us to clarify the scope of theoretical statements relating to ‘self-organization processes’ in nerve networks, the existence of ‘ordered structures’, the appearance of ‘solitary waves’ and so on; except in the case of single neurons, these are almost always “metaphors,” “figures of speech,” or ‘simulations’ that mathematics creates using “toy models” of processes, which in reality are far from being understood in either their general aspects or their particular mechanisms.

It is interesting to note that these mathematical theories can largely be traced back to a single general scheme, a sort of family tree that gives

rise to various specific theories when more specialised conditions are introduced (An der Heiden, 1980). In this general scheme, Hebb's hypothesis (1949) of temporal variation in synaptic coupling coefficients plays a crucial role, with networks exhibiting exciting temporal evolutions.

The main features of Hebb's model (1949) can be summarised as follows:

a) behaviour can be identified with the activity patterns of a neural network; b) the learning process consists of the variation of the neural interconnection coefficients; c) memory is the state of the coefficients at a given moment; d) the values of these coefficients tend to be stable depending on the parameters of the network and the nature of the external stimuli (Guazzo, 2024a,b,c).

Some studies (Feigenbaum, 1983; Cohen & Grossberg, 1983) indicate that attempts to construct an adequate model of learning processes based on Hebb's hypothesis encounter significant mathematical challenges. Indicate that attempts to build an adequate model of learning processes based on Hebb's hypothesis encounter significant mathematical challenges. A possible solution to the problem can be found by using the continuous mathematical model of morphogenesis in self-organising systems (Guazzo, 1987b). In this way, the learning process will no longer be considered as a transaction of interconnection coefficients but will be identified as the process of creating a dissipative structure (Guazzo, 2024a,b,c; Easton & Gordon, 1984).

This suggests that the theories constructed so far can be divided into two main strands: on the one hand, those that emphasize, in various ways, the role of individual neurons within the nervous network and, on the other, those that explicitly renounce this aspect and use only global descriptions based on a small number of 'collective' variables that satisfy not too complicated equations. Among the theories of the first strand, it is necessary to mention the works based on the analogy with the theory of 'spin glasses', which has numerous applications in physics. These studies have had some success in constructing a rudimentary model of the

functioning of an associative memory capable of categorisation (Binder & Young, 1986).

Theories of the second strand are derived from the classic works of Wilson and Cowan (1973) and are typically expressed in the language of partial differential equation theory. Thanks to the mathematical tools they employ, these theories are formally very similar to the models of self-organising processes studied in recent years by many authors (Belintsev, 1983; Auchmuty & Nicolis, 1975; Basar, Flohr, Haken, & Mandell, 1983).

One might naturally wonder what the point of all this theoretical effort is if it is, after all, just a matter of "metaphors" that are far removed from actual reality. The answer to this question lies in the observation that 'simulations' can, sooner or later, become 'models' and thus acquire great utility. To be precise, this transformation can take place in two ways. The first occurs when the 'simulation' considers so many particularities of real processes that it becomes an actual 'model'. The second way, which is conceptually no less critical, occurs when the "simulation" becomes the guide for the actual construction of an artificial system that conforms precisely to the principles of the theory. In this way, the "toy theory" becomes a real "model" for the system we have built.

Conclusions

The fundamental goals of AI research are not so much to build systems that exactly "imitate" humans, but rather to create systems that are "better" than current computers. In other words, it is not necessary to have an exact copy of a system such as the human brain, which, even if it is vastly superior to current computers (in terms of cognitive processes), is severely handicapped in certain other respects (computing speed). What matters most is to have artificial systems that are "useful" to us, with which we can interact "naturally", enabling computers to simulate complex "reasoning" and other cognitive activities (solving problems, learning from mistakes, etc.) that until now have been exclusive to natural intelligence.

Seen from this perspective, Artificial Intelligence is hugely important: it helps us navigate a sea of

extremely changeable and shifting phenomena that are, at the same time, vital to our lives.

References

- an der Heiden, U. (1980). *Analysis of Neural Networks* (Lecture Notes in Biomathematics, Vol. 35). Berlin; Heidelberg; New York: Springer-Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-45517-9>
- Auchmuty, J. F. G., & Nicolis, G. (1975). Bifurcation analysis of nonlinear reaction-diffusion equations. I: Evolution equations and steady-state solutions. *Bulletin of Mathematical Biology*, 37, 325–365. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02462929>
- Basar, E., Flohr, H., Haken, H., & Mandell, A. J. (1983). *Synergetics of the Brain: Proceedings of the International Symposium on Synergetics at Schloss Elman*. Berlin: Springer.
- Belintsev, B. N. (1983). Dissipative structures and the problem of biological pattern formation. *Soviet Physics Uspekhi*, 26, 775–800. <https://doi.org/10.1070/PU1983v026n09ABEH004492>
- Binder, K., & Young, A. P. (1986). Spin glasses: Experimental facts, theoretical concepts, and open questions. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 58(4), 801–976. <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.58.801>
- Cohen, M. A., & Grossberg, S. (1983). Absolute stability of global pattern formation and parallel memory storage by competitive neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, 13, 815–823. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.1983.6313075>
- Easton, P., & Gordon, P. E. (1984). Stabilization of Hebbian neural nets by inhibitory learning. *Biological Cybernetics*, 51, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00336182>
- Ermentrout, G. B., & Cowan, J. D. (1980). Secondary bifurcation in neuronal nets. *SIAM Journal on Applied Mathematics*, 12, 323–340. <https://doi.org/10.1137/0139028>
- Feigenbaum, M. J. (1983). Universal behaviour in nonlinear systems. *Physica D*, 7, 16–39. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2789\(83\)90112-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2789(83)90112-4)
- Guazzo, G. M. (1987a). *Cibernetica e processi mentali*. Bari: Sipcasdia Publishers.
- Guazzo, G. M. (1987b). Dissipative structures emerging within an abstract model of neural network. In E. R. Caianiello (Ed.), *Physics of Cognitive Processes* (pp. 163–170). Singapore: World Scientific Publishing Co.
- Guazzo, G. M. (1993). A ‘morphogenetic’ model of learning. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 8(3), 257–263. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-0779\(93\)90070-H](https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-0779(93)90070-H)
- Guazzo, G. M. (2024a). A ‘Systemic’ Model of a mind-body interaction. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences (EJTAS)*, 2(1), 1–5. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(1\).17](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).17)
- Guazzo, G. M. (2024b). An Abstract Description of Learning as a Morphogenetic Process. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences (EJTAS)*, 2(2), 102–107. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(2\).09](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(2).09)
- Guazzo, G. M. (2024c). Dissipative Structures and Self-organization Process in an Abstract Model of Neural Network. *European Journal of Applied Science, Engineering and Technology*, 2(2), 17–21. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).02](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).02)
- Harth, E. (1983). Order and chaos in neural system: An approach to the dynamic of higher brain function. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, 13, 782–789. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.1983.6313072>
- Hebb, D. O. (1949). *The Organization of Behavior*. New York: Wiley.
- Morin, E. (2007). *On Complexity*. Cresskill, NJ: Hampton Press.
- Pessa, E. (1987). Introduzione a Guazzo, G. M. *Cibernetica e processi mentali*. Bari: Sipcasdia Publishers.
- Pessa, E. (1992). *Intelligenza artificiale*. Torino: Boringhieri.
- Prigogine, I., & Stengers, I. (1984). *Order Out of Chaos: Man’s New Dialogue with Nature*. New York: Bantam New Age Books.

Prigogine, I., & Stengers, I. (1997). *The End of Certainty: Time, Chaos, and the New Laws of Nature*. New York: Free Press.

Rosen, R. (1986). Causal structures in brains and machines. *International Journal of General Systems*, 12(2), 107–126.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03081078608934929>

Wilson, H. R., & Cowan, J. D. (1973). A mathematical theory of the functional dynamics of cortical and thalamic nervous tissue. *Kybernetik*, 13, 55–80.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00288786>